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ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS OF AGUA NUEVA AND PIMIENTA SHALE FORMATIONS DEVELOPMENT IN MEXICO

Serbina E.V.

PhD in geology, Independent Expert, Mexico City, Mexico

Bochkarev V.A.

Director on Exploration and Development

LUKOIL Upstream Mexico, Mexico

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-3642-6561>

Abstract

At present, no type of energy generation can be considered entirely environmentally friendly. This article discusses the strategic role of shale hydrocarbons in Mexico's transition toward truly renewable energy sources. Until recently, the development of the Pimienta shale formation through hydraulic fracturing (fracking) faced an informal prohibition in Mexico. However, advances in extraction technologies successfully applied in the United States and Argentina—make it possible to achieve both economic profitability and environmental safety in shale hydrocarbon production. The implementation of shale projects in Mexico could become a key driver of national economic growth, ensure energy independence, and provide financial resources for future investments in genuinely “green” energy development.

Keyword: Mexico, shale hydrocarbons, Pimienta shale formation, Agua Nueva shale formation, hydraulic fracturing (fracking), catagenesis, shale gas, shale oil, production, energy transition, renewable energy, energy security, geothermal energy, electricity generation mix.

Despite various geopolitical and economic upheavals, global demand for energy continues to grow. According to the Global Energy Review 2025 published by the International Energy Agency (IEA), global energy demand in 2024 increased by 2.2 %, which is significantly higher than the average annual growth rate of the previous decade (≈ 1.3 % per year) [1]. At the same time, “green” energy policies are becoming increasingly important worldwide. The central theme of the global environmental agenda the carbon footprint has, in many cases, become a subject of political and economic manipulation [2].

On the other hand, between 2035 and 2040, a sharp decline in oil production from conventional reservoirs is expected, which will likely lead to an increase

in oil prices. During this period, the world will also reach the peak production of shale oil, which, however, will be insufficient to fully offset the overall decline in output from aging conventional fields [4, 7].

The role of shale hydrocarbon resources will inevitably continue to grow due to their operational flexibility and the fact that their total resources and reserves are approximately twice those of conventional hydrocarbons.

This will shift the operational focus toward countries such as the United States, Argentina,

Mexico, Canada, Brazil, Russia, Poland, China, and Australia, all of which possess significant reserves of these types of hydrocarbon sources (**Fig. 1**) [3, 7, 9].

Fig. 1 - Distribution of the world's shale basins (Source: EIA) [3, 7]

It is expected that the peak of shale play activity will be reached between 2030 and 2040. Heavy oil and bitumen will begin to play an increasingly important role between 2030 and 2035, when their development will become economically feasible across all key parameters.

By 2040, the price of oil may reach 170 USD per barrel [3, 7]. Rising consumption combined with the limited availability of low breakeven reserves will exert additional upward pressure on prices.

At present (end of 2025), the oil price is around 63 USD per barrel, which makes the production of shale oil economically viable across all major shale plays in the United States, Canada, and Argentina.

Argentina is currently the only country in South America conducting commercial shale hydrocarbon production from the Vaca Muerta formation. As of mid-2025, production reached approximately 0.5 MMbbl/day of oil and about 875 MMft³/day of gas.

By 2025–2027, maintaining current production rates and oil prices, Argentina is expected to double its oil output and significantly increase gas production solely through shale development projects. In 2024, Argentina completely ceased oil imports.

The Eagle Ford shale formation extends into Mexican territory, occurring at approximately the same burial depths and under similar thermobaric conditions as on the U.S. side (Fig. 2). The assessment and subsequent planning of exploration and development were based on data from adjacent U.S. fields Red Hawk (shale oil), Blue Hawk (shale condensate), and Hawkville (shale gas) in southern Texas as well as from analogous fields and IHS (2014) data for wells drilled into the Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva formations on the Mexican side: Chucla-1, Durian-1, Emergente-1, and Montanes-1.

Fig. 2 – Zoning of hydrocarbon generation on the structural map of the Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva Formation top. 1 – contour lines, ft; 2 – pilot area; 3 – boundary isoresplines of the main hydrocarbon generation zones; 4 – area of source rocks within oil generation conditions (“oil window”); 5 – same, “gas-condensate window”; 6 – “gas window”; 7 – Gulf of Mexico offshore area; 8 – wells: (a) located in Mexico, (b) in oil fields, (c) in gas and gas-condensate fields; 9 – field boundaries; 10 – U.S.–Mexico state border [3, 8].

Experience

from the development of shale deposits worldwide allows identifying both the advantages and limitations of such projects in Mexico. The Agua Nueva shale formation demonstrates several favorable factors: a large areal extent, substantial volumes of organic-rich shale (high TOC), and low initial licensing costs.

Additional advantages include the presence of numerous developed shale fields across the U.S. border and the accumulated operational experience; minimal

exploration expenditures for non-structural traps; reliable geological data from earlier surveys in the region; and proximity to markets supported by relatively developed infrastructure. The presence of condensate and light oil ensures high project profitability regardless of gas prices.

However, several constraints may negatively affect shale development in this region. These include the lack of domestic expertise in shale hydrocarbon exploitation, geological uncertainty regarding the properties

and productivity of the Eagle Ford /Agua Nueva formations on the Mexican side, high initial production costs, and rapid decline rates of shale wells compared to conventional fields.

In addition, governmental restrictions on large-scale hydraulic fracturing (fracking) remain in place, limiting development potential. Reported initial production rates from shale wells in the U.S. Eagle Ford Formation range from 3.5–17.5MMft³/day of gas, 350–2800 bbl/day of condensate, and 210–850 bbl/day of oil [3].

The continuation of the Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva formation into Mexican territory exhibits high potential for natural gas and condensate production. Preliminary assessments suggest that the resource base in Mexico could reach hundreds of billions of cubic meters of gas and tens of millions of tonnes of liquid hydrocarbons [8].

The Pimienta Formation is the primary source rock in eastern Mexico, genetically linked to nearly all hydrocarbon accumulations in overlying Eocene, Oligocene, Miocene, Albian, Cenomanian, and Upper Jurassic strata hosted in conventional reservoirs and traps. Within the Tamaulipas, Veracruz, and Tabasco regions, the Pimienta Formation shows high potential for shale hydrocarbon development (**Fig. 3**) [6].

Nevertheless, its productivity remains poorly understood. Between 2010 and 2019, only 25 wells were drilled into the Pimienta Formation, including five horizontal wells with multistage hydraulic fracturing in the Tampico–Misantla Basin. These demonstrated average initial oil flow rates of approximately 900 bbl/day, with the Kaneni-1EXP well achieving a maximum rate of 1932 bbl/day after 17 stages of fracturing.

According to drilling data from wells targeting the Pimienta Formation within the western part of the Tampico Basin, an anomalously high geothermal gradient and abnormally elevated reservoir pressures have been identified in the Tithonian strata of the formation. These anomalies are attributed to geodynamic and thermal influences exerted by the Sierra Madre mountain system [6].

A high-standing viscoplastic magmatic focus, along with its convective eastward movement, caused extreme thermal effects and accelerated catagenesis (hypercatagenesis) of organic-mineral matter (OM) within the Pimienta Formation.

This process occurs in the contact zone beginning at depths of approximately 500 m, corresponding to stage MC₅ (the main gas-generation zone), thus bypassing the stages of protocatagenesis (PC_{1–3}), early and middle mesocatagenesis (MC_{1–4}), and the main oil-generation zone (MC₁–MC₂).

Fig. 3 – Oil and gas basins of eastern Mexico (onshore) where the Pimienta Formation is distributed [6].

Approximately along the coastline of the Gulf of Mexico runs the boundary between the main gas-generation and oil-generation zones. Beyond this boundary, the Pimienta Formation dips toward the offshore area, transitioning to the regional catagenetic scheme typical for the basin, characterized by a normal geothermal gradient [5].

According to drilling data from wells targeting the **Pimienta Formation** within the western part of the **Tampico Basin**, an **anomalously high geothermal gradient** and **abnormally elevated reservoir pressures** have been identified. These anomalies are caused by **geodynamic and thermal influences** from the **Sierra Madre mountain system** [6].

A high-standing viscoplastic magmatic focus and its convective eastward migration have resulted in extreme heating and accelerated catagenesis (hypercatagenesis) of organic-mineral matter (OM) within the Pimienta Formation. This thermal overprint occurs in the contact zone from depths as shallow as 500 m, corresponding to stage MC₅ (main gas generation zone), bypassing the stages of protocatagenesis (PC₁₋₃), early and middle mesocatagenesis (MC₁₋₄), and the main oil generation zone (MC₁-MC₂).

Approximately along the Gulf of Mexico coastline lies the boundary between the main gas- and oil-generation zones, beyond which the Pimienta Formation dips seaward and transitions into the regional catagenetic scheme characterized by a normal geothermal gradient [5].

The current zonation scheme of hydrocarbon generation and accumulation within the Pimienta Formation in the Tampico Province, compiled on the basis of deep-drilling data [10], is supported by results of hydraulic fracturing (HF) performed in five wells except for the deep interval corresponding to light oil (MC_2 – MC_3).

In the Horcones-8127 and Furbero-4354 wells, light oil with a density of 37–38° API was obtained, indicating that the light-oil boundary shifts eastward, approximately along the Gulf coastline.

The boundaries of the main gas- and oil-generation zones are further confirmed by data from wells Pankiwi-1 (49°API) and Kaneni-1 (39°API).

Therefore, within the Tamaulipas and Veracruz provinces, production from the Pimienta Formation is expected to consist primarily of light oil with a density of 37–40°API, whereas in the western part, adjacent to the Sierra Madre system, production will mainly comprise dry gas and condensate.

The Pimienta Formation, which is approximately twice as thick as the Eagle Ford, combined with the im-

plementation of cyclic development strategies [3, 4] including repeated hydraulic fracturing of existing wells could yield higher cumulative production per well than in U.S. shale plays. This would reduce the number of new wells required and significantly improve the economic efficiency of shale hydrocarbon development in Mexico (Fig. 4) [6].

The initiation of shale development activities in the Pimienta Formation in Mexico by 2027 would allow commercial production to begin by 2028, with expected additional output of 0.4–1.3 MMbbl/day of oil by 2030.

By 2040–2050, production in the Tamaulipas, Veracruz, and Tabasco provinces could reach 2–3.3 MMbbl/day, sufficient to fully meet the country's domestic oil demand and to ensure Mexico's energy security until approximately 2060–2080, assuming the continuation of cyclic shale development under current consumption levels.

Starting from 2032, Mexico would be capable of exporting surplus oil to the United States and to countries of Central and South America [6].

Fig. 4 – Principle of cyclic development of shale hydrocarbon reservoirs [3, 4, 6, 7, 8].

Considering that the Pimienta Formation lies within the gas-, condensate-, and light oil-generation zones, gas production (both dry and associated) may reach 2–4 Bft³/day by 2030. Together with the Eagle Ford / Agua Nueva shale gas development project extending into Mexico [7], this could ensure long-term energy security in the gas sector by 2033. Between 2032 and 2035, additional gas turbine power plants (GTPPs) may be commissioned in the Tampico, Veracruz, and Tabasco provinces, utilizing growing volumes of free gas production, which would significantly reduce electricity costs for consumers.

Until recently, there existed an informal governmental ban in Mexico on hydraulic fracturing (fracking), particularly on large-scale operations targeting the Pimienta Formation. This restriction was primarily based on early environmental data from the first years of shale development in the United States, when serious environmental incidents related to extensive fracking operations were indeed observed.

An analysis of the environmental situation associated with shale play development in the United States and other regions of the world [2, 9] shows that modern advanced technologies, combined with higher oil and gas prices in recent years, now allow for both economically viable and environmentally safe shale hydrocarbon production through the following measures:

- Application of directional hydraulic fracturing to prevent fracture propagation into overlying aquifers.
- Reduction of the toxicity of fracturing fluids.
- Water treatment and reuse for hydraulic fracturing operations.
- Construction of seawater desalination plants to supply shale projects located near the Gulf of Mexico.
- Continuous environmental monitoring of groundwater, surface water, soil, and air.
- Seismic monitoring and tracer studies to assess the impact of industrial HF on induced seismicity within shale play regions.

The implementation of cyclic shale development could substantially reduce the number of producing wells, thereby decreasing the environmental footprint on subsurface resources and the surrounding environment [3, 7, 8].

The development of shale projects in the Tampico, Veracruz, and Tabasco states would create tens of thousands of jobs. The cities of Tampico, Veracruz, and Villahermosa could become major centers of Mexico's oil and gas industry. Veracruz, in particular, could evolve into a regional hub for shale hydrocarbon production and host a new refinery for processing shale oil volumes.

In Tampico, modernization of the existing refinery could allow for the processing of heavy oil, co-produced with shale hydrocarbons from the Pánuco, Altamira, and Ébano blocks.

To ensure adequate water supply for hydraulic fracturing, water treatment and reclamation plants may be constructed under a "1 liter for HF – 2 liters of purified water" principle to offset freshwater use.

These projects could significantly lower fuel and petroleum product costs in Mexico and support the export of petrochemical products to Central and South American markets. The main role of Mexico's government agencies in successfully implementing shale projects in the Tampico, Veracruz, and Tabasco regions should be to ensure competition and open market participation for drilling companies, reducing the average cost of drilling and completion to 5–8 MMUSD per well [6].

Mexico has declared a goal to achieve 45% of electricity generation from renewable energy sources (RES): solar, wind, hydro, and others by 2030 [11]. However, the implementation of renewable energy projects continues to face serious challenges, including aging transmission infrastructure, lack of energy storage facilities, regulatory uncertainty for private and foreign investors, high financial risks, and social and environmental conflicts at project sites.

While small-scale distributed solar projects (e.g., rooftop installations) remain economically viable even without direct subsidies due to tax incentives, large private renewable projects have stagnated since 2018, following the withdrawal of government subsidies. The federal government prioritizes building renewable capacity through the state-owned utility CFE, rather than through private investors. According to Ember (2024), the combined share of solar and wind power in Mexico's electricity generation is $\approx 13\%$ [12].

A particularly ambitious initiative is the Plan Sonora, a government-led project to construct a 1 GW solar megastation. The first 120 MW phase was launched in 2023, yet the project faces public resistance, as it focuses primarily on infrastructure, logistics, and lithium extraction, rather than on community-based clean energy generation [13].

Although renewable energy sources - solar, wind, and hydro are often labeled as "clean," their environmental impacts are not eliminated, but rather transformed. For example, solar panel production requires significant resources, including rare earth metals, sili-

con, and high energy inputs for smelting and processing. Moreover, end-of-life management of photovoltaic (PV) panels remains an unresolved issue: panels contain toxic substances such as lead, cadmium, and tellurium, and their average service life is ~ 25 years, after which most are discarded into landfills. According to the IEA/IRENA Task 12 report [13], by 2050, global PV waste could reach ~ 78 MMtonnes. As noted in "How to tackle the looming challenge of solar PV panel recycling" (PNAS, 2025) [14], only $\sim 10\%$ of retired PV panels are currently recycled, with the remainder sent to landfills, burial, or incineration. In Mexico's Jalisco state, the first PV recycling plant is still under development, projected to process 1,000 tonnes per year with investment of ~ 12 – 15 million pesos. As a non-profit initiative, the facility will likely require state subsidies, tax exemptions, or grants, as do most "green" projects at early stages.

Wind energy also entails significant material inputs - concrete, steel, and large land areas and can affect bird populations and local landscapes. In 2024, the share of wind energy in Mexico's total generation was approximately 6% [15]. Wind projects face grid, infrastructure, and land-rights challenges, as well as social resistance. At least two major projects: Gunaa Sicarú Wind Farm and Mareña Renovables Wind Project with a combined cost of around 1.5 BUSD, were cancelled due to local and indigenous community protests [16].

Hydropower in Mexico is undergoing structural decline, driven by aging infrastructure, water scarcity, community opposition, and lack of investment incentives. Hydroelectric plants are not fully "green," as they alter river ecosystems, disrupt fish migration, and affect local climates. They have also become less reliable energy sources, as seasonal flow variations can cause 30–50% output reductions during drought years. According to CONAGUA, reservoir levels have decreased by 20–30% on average over the past decade, particularly in central and northern states [17].

The La Parota project (Guerrero) was suspended after protests over the potential flooding of 17 villages and the relocation of $\sim 25,000$ residents. Such conflicts have created a public perception of hydropower as "socially risky", especially following failed wind energy cases (e.g., Oaxaca). According to CFE (Comisión Federal de Electricidad), about 70% of Mexico's hydropower plants require major rehabilitation, but no funding has been allocated. National energy strategies have shifted priority toward solar and wind, which require less land and fewer social negotiations.

Promising opportunities remain only for small-scale hydropower (1–10 MW) in southern mountain regions with stable river flow and minimal resettlement needs.

All of Mexico's nuclear power generation is concentrated in a single operating facility - the Laguna Verde Nuclear Power Plant (Veracruz), constructed in the 1980s with U.S. assistance. The plant's total capacity is 1640 MW (two GE BWR-5 reactors). It remains fully dependent on foreign technology, equipment, and nuclear fuel, primarily from the United States and Japan. According to the IAEA and

independent industry reviews, the average cost of electricity generation at Laguna Verde is 100–120 USD per MWh, compared to 40–50 USD per MWh for large-scale solar power projects [18, 19].

Thus, nuclear energy remains the least competitive low-carbon source in Mexico due to high capital costs, fuel import dependency, and the absence of economies of scale. There is still no centralized repository for radioactive waste; spent fuel is stored temporarily on-site at Laguna Verde. Moreover, Mexico lacks national legislation defining a long-term radioactive waste management strategy.

Thus, the transition to “green energy” is not so much a path toward complete environmental purity as it is a search for balance between energy security, sustainability, and minimal ecosystem disruption.

According to 2019 data, Mexico ranks sixth globally after the United States, the Philippines, Indonesia, Turkey, and New Zealand—in installed geothermal power capacity, which is estimated at 951 MW. The largest geothermal plants, Cerro Prieto II and Cerro Prieto III, each have an installed capacity of 220 MW. Although geothermal energy is classified as *renewable and green*, studies [20, 21] indicate that in the area of the Cerro Prieto geothermal complex (Baja California, Mexico), mercury concentrations in surface soils range from 0.01 to 0.26 mg/kg. The same studies report that geothermal brine leaks lead to elevated concentrations of elements such as arsenic (up to 8 mg/L) and boron compounds (up to 125 mg/L) both within and up to 10 km beyond the geothermal field. These findings suggest that geothermal projects, despite being labeled as “renewable and clean,” can pose localized environmental risks, including soil and water

contamination by heavy metals and toxic elements. For Mexico where geothermal fields are situated in volcanically active regions, often adjacent to rural communities such research holds particular importance.

Mexico has made official commitments to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by approximately 35% by 2030 relative to the *business-as-usual (BAU)* scenario. Environmental issues, however, are often subject to politicization and speculative interpretation, overshadowing scientific evidence. Recent studies increasingly highlight that higher atmospheric CO₂ concentrations can in fact promote plant biomass growth, a phenomenon known as the CO₂ fertilization effect. According to Zhu et al. (2016), elevated CO₂ concentrations exert a strong stimulatory influence on photosynthesis, leading to a global increase in vegetation biomass by approximately 10% over the past three decades. This effect has been further confirmed by other studies (Donohue et al., 2013; Le Quéré et al., 2022), which observed accelerated biomass accumulation and increased leaf area index particularly in semi-arid regions of the world.

The Mexican government’s environmental commitments, shaped largely by the global green agenda, contrast with current economic and technical realities. At this stage, shale hydrocarbon projects represent a more economically and environmentally rational option. The profitability of shale projects is considerably higher: shale wells typically achieve full payback within 1–2 years, whereas solar and wind farms require 10–15 years to reach break-even.

Natural gas-fired power plants (Fig. 5) produce more than 60% of Mexico’s total electricity generation.

Fig. 5 – Electricity generation mix in Mexico (%), IEA, Mexico 2024 [22]

At the same time, **Mexico imports most of its gas from the United States** - about 5.5 Bft³/day (2019) through pipelines and receives **liquefied natural gas (LNG)** from the U.S., Qatar, Nigeria, and Peru. This occurs despite the country’s **significant untapped domestic reserves of natural (shale) gas**. Such a situation creates a **paradoxical dependency on external suppliers**, despite the availability of local resources. It

reinforces **Mexico’s energy vulnerability and price exposure** to the U.S. market while simultaneously **hindering the development of a self-sufficient national energy sector** and slowing the transition toward **genuinely sustainable energy** that is, energy systems with **minimal environmental externalities**. The electricity

generation mix reflects the structure of power generation by source that is, which technologies actually deliver electricity to the national grid (**Table 1**).

Its composition directly mirrors a country's dependence on fossil fuels, the extent of renewable energy

integration, climatic and seasonal conditions (e.g., variations in hydropower output), and the technological maturity of its power system (for example, the share of modern combined-cycle gas turbines compared to outdated fuel-oil units).

Table 1

Share of energy sources in Mexico's electricity generation mix (% of total generation)

Year	Gas %	Oil/Diesel, %	Coal, %	Hydro, %	Wind %	Sun %	Nuclear %	Others (geo-, bio-)%	Source
2000	16.7	49.2	9.2	17.3	0	0	4.5	3.1	(SENER). <i>Balance Nacional de Energía 2000</i>
2003	54.5	12.3	13	14.5	0	0	2.4	3.2	SENER). <i>Balance Nacional de Energía 2003</i>
2010	50.9	15.6	13.2	15.1	0.1	0	2.4	2.7	<i>Balance Nacional de Energía 2010</i> (SENER) + IEA
2015	59.9	10.1	10.9	9.9	3	0.3	4	1.9	CEICData. Mexico, (SENER 2016)
2020	60	10	5	8.5	6	3	4	3.5	<i>Our World in Data / IEA 2020</i>
2022	59	8	8	10	6	6	3	0,3	<i>SENER PRODESEN 2023-2037</i>
2023	61	7	5	9	9	7	3	1	IEA / Ember 2024
2024	62	7.4	7.6	6.2	5.1	6.2	3	2.5	(IEA). Mexico
2035	75	4	3	4	5	5	1	3	Author's forecast

In the case of Mexico, the electricity generation mix is a truly key indicator, as electric power accounts for approximately 20 % of the nation's final energy consumption. The structure of electricity generation is closely linked to the energy policies of the state-owned utility CFE and the Ministry of Energy (SENER). However, the electricity mix only shows the composition of power generation—what fuels and technologies produce electricity.

Electricity itself represents only one-fifth of total energy use, while the remaining ≈ 80 % is associated with other sectors:

- Transport: gasoline, diesel, jet fuel, natural gas, biofuels;
- Industrial heat and steam: oil, coal, and gas used for heating, smelting, cement, and metal production;
- Residential and commercial energy: cooking and heating fuels such as gas, wood, coal, and biomass;
- Agriculture and extractive industries: diesel, oil, and gas used off-grid.

Indeed, the “green transformation” in Mexico (as elsewhere in the world) primarily concerns the electricity sector that is, how electricity is produced. Other sectors: transportation, industry, heating, and agriculture remain largely dependent on fossil fuels. Integrating renewable energy sources (RES) requires new transmission lines and energy-storage facilities, which means additional costs. Solar projects frequently encounter community resistance related to land disputes and leasing conflicts. In contrast, for shale hydrocarbon pro-

jects, the pipeline and transmission infrastructure already exists (the northern regions are connected to Texas), and no new gas-pipeline construction is required, since new gas-fired power plants (GTPPs) can be built within producing regions such as Tamaulipas, Veracruz, and Tabasco. Land for shale projects is often state-owned, and Pemex, the national oil company, obtains access through federal regulation.

Renewables depend on sunlight and wind, require backup generation capacity, and typically rely on government subsidies. Shale gas, by contrast, provides a stable and high-capacity source of electricity generation and reduces Mexico's energy dependence on the United States. The development of the Agua Nueva and Pimienta shale formations, beginning in 2027, could allow Mexico to produce an additional 3–5 Bft³/day of gas by 2030 and to achieve long-term gas self-sufficiency by 2033, even enabling exports to neighboring Latin American countries. By 2032, up to 75 % of Mexico's electricity could be generated from natural gas, currently the cleanest and most efficient fossil fuel available.

Therefore, the most effective and economically sound energy policy for Mexico in the coming decades should focus on the development and production of shale hydrocarbons. This strategy will strengthen technological capacity and create a foundation for a gradual transition toward truly renewable, environmentally safe, and low-waste energy sources, including hydrogen, electromagnetic, and nano-ether energy systems [23].

Conclusion

Mexico's energy future will depend on achieving a **rational balance between environmental sustainability and national energy security**.

While the global green agenda emphasizes the rapid transition to renewable energy sources, **technological, economic, and infrastructural realities** demonstrate that **fossil fuels—particularly shale hydrocarbons—will remain essential** for the country's development in the medium term. The exploitation of the **Pimienta** and **Agua Nueva** shale formations offers Mexico a unique opportunity to strengthen its **domestic energy base, reduce dependency on imports, and secure the financial resources** needed for the long-term development of truly clean energy technologies.

At the same time, the experience of the **United States** and **Argentina** shows that modern shale development can be both **economically viable and environmentally responsible** when advanced technologies are applied—such as **directional hydraulic fracturing, water recycling, and environmental monitoring**.

For Mexico, the adoption of these practices would not only minimize environmental risks but also generate **tens of thousands of jobs** and stimulate **technological innovation** across related industries.

By 2033, the **combined production** from shale formations could **fully ensure Mexico's gas self-sufficiency**, and by 2040–2050 the country may become a **net exporter of hydrocarbons**, achieving **energy independence** and **price stability** for decades ahead.

In the long run, the revenues and technological expertise gained from shale energy projects can provide the foundation for a **gradual, science-based transition to next-generation renewable systems** including **hydrogen, electromagnetic, and nano-ether technologies**.

Thus, Mexico's strategic path lies not in rejecting hydrocarbons, but in **integrating them intelligently** into a diversified, sustainable energy framework that balances **economic efficiency, environmental responsibility, and technological progress**.

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